

**Alice Munro's Short Story loneliness lead to happiness through Hateship,
Friendship, Courtship, Loveship, Marriage**

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Abstract

Alice Munro, a prominent Canadian literary figure, was born in Ontario, in the country's southwest, on July 10, 1931. Her skill in crafting short stories earned her recognition as "the master of the contemporary short-story." The main focus of Alice Munro's works is her depiction of the challenges that women encounter in their daily lives and as members of society. Her female protagonists engage in unusual relationships and encounter unusual circumstances in her works. The majority of her artwork are influenced by concepts of independence and choice. Her female characters occasionally find it difficult to defy social expectations. It is evident how discrimination against women develops when they find it difficult to make their own decisions. The concept of Hateship, Friendship, Courtship, Loveship, and Marriage centers on the characters' connections with happiness, loneliness, and unexpected life changes. The central theme employed by author Munro is loneliness, which is thought to be experienced by the female protagonists. The three major female characters in this short story—Johana, Sabitha, and Edith—

seem to be lonely at first, but by the conclusion, they are helping each other to accomplish their goals. The study's conclusion covered how they overcame their loneliness to receive compassion and how they continued to have positive relationships with other people. They surprised Johanna by making her life pleasant with their humorous letter. Hence, the loneliness problem that eventually results in happiness.

Key Words: Letter, Hoax, Loneliness, Friendship, Loveship, Happiness

Alice Munro, a prominent Canadian literary figure, was born in Ontario, in the country's southwest, on July 10, 1931. Her skill in crafting short stories earned her recognition as "the master of the contemporary short-story." She became the first Canadian to attain such a magnificent feat when she was commended for her literary Noble Prize for Literature in the year 2013. In addition to the Noble Prize, she received additional notable literary honors and acknowledgment for her outstanding creative work on a national and worldwide scale.

In 1968, her first collection of short stories gained recognition in the literary world. Her other well-known works, including "Lives of Girls and Women," "Too Much Happiness," "Hateship, Friendship, Courtship, Loveship, Marriage," "Dear Life," "Open Secrets," and so on, came after. Her writings were frequently published in well-read periodicals such as Parish Review, Atlantic Monthly, and New Yorker.

Canadian author Alice Munro developed a picture of reality in all its complexity by writing about ordinary individuals in typical situations. The select story, Hateship, Friendship, Courtship, Loveship, Marriage, is explored in depth in this article.

The story titled "Hateship, Friendship, Courtship, Loveship, Marriage" begins with two best friends named Sabitha and Edith deciding to play a practical joke on Sabitha's housemaid, Johanna. They begin by pretending to be Sabitha's father, Ken, and writing her letters. Unaware Johanna, a self-sufficient but reclusive person, begins to open up in her letters by sharing with 'Ken' details of her painful history. She quits her work, sends him part of Ken's stuff, and then relocates to care for Ken one day. When Johanna arrives at his apartment, Ken stares at her strangely, not understanding why she wants to take care of him. As time passes, they develop into true friends, and Johanna stops being a lonely woman as she has found her family.

Johanna is unaware that letters have been written to her under the father's name by Sabitha and Edith, a friend.

Johanna talks to "Ken" in the letters about her wretched and solitary past. Working as a housekeeper for Mr. McCauley and his granddaughter Sabitha, Johanna is an unmarried, plain, impoverished woman. Sabitha's mother passed away, and her father, Ken Boudreau, suffers from poverty and often pleads his father-in-law for money from where he resides. Edith is a blacksmith's daughter who is bored with her restrictive blue-collar job and is friends with Sabitha.

In an elaborate deception, Edith and Sabitha pretend to be Johanna's father and Sabitha's love letters. Johanna utilizes her substantial money to fly to Ken's remote location in rural Canada after becoming convinced by the letters that he will marry her. After learning that Ken is unwell, she tenderly tends to his medical requirements. Johanna takes the initiative and makes plans for them to begin a new life after seeing that Ken is impotent over his own life. After exchanging letters, Johanna feels compelled to go to Ken's place in order to care for him, as he is by himself and hardly able to look after himself because of his depression at losing his wife.

Johanna makes the decision to mail some of Ken's things to his current residence in Saskatchewan. The writer thinks that making a significant life change is an attempt to go farther away from the loneliness that was limiting her. She quits her work because she wants to move to Saskatchewan. (HFCLM 10-17). He takes her to his residence in Saskatchewan. Ken doesn't understand why a stranger is visiting his home. Ken is clueless about Johanna's background and her unexpected arrival at his home (HFCLM 42-45).

Though she is still completely unknown to him, Ken finds it hard to understand why a lady who has been sending him deceptive letters is trying to take care of him in his home. Johanna is still a stranger to Ken, thus at first, his ignorance of her causes him to have issues. Along the way, he befriends her and opens up to her, allowing her to take care of him. (HFCLM 47-51).

The writer is certain that Johanna feels hopeful now that she has a buddy in life because Ken has opened up to her and shown her that there is a way for her to be happy. Unexpectedly, the narrative jumps ahead two years, to a time when Johanna has given birth to a

son named Omar from Ken. “Edith no longer fears being found out about the forgery she and Sabitha practiced; she does reflect on this irony that “where, on the list of things she planned to achieve in her life, was there any mention of her being responsible for the existence on earth of a person named Omar?”(The Fiction of Alice Munro: An Appreciation, P.133)

After finding a lifelong friend who has given her a family she has never had, Johanna's happiness is now within grasp. This writer draws the conclusion that, contrary to popular belief, this particular narrative tells of how loneliness makes a lady strong but alone until she meets a companion who completely transforms her lonely life.

The story turns when she decides to move to take care of Ken. She even quits her work and gives him his personal furniture to demonstrate how passionate she is about their friendship. Even yet, she is still unaware that the two youngsters are pulling a practical joke on her. Her move demonstrates her willingness to go to any lengths for her new friend, "Ken," and her pursuit of this bond in the hopes of reviving the happiness she hasn't had in a long time. Notably, Ken's perspective is used to illustrate Johanna's life transformation this time. “...Two women, actually, a young one and an older one who knew about each other and were ready to tear other’s hair out.... Perhaps a solution had arrived for that, as well” (49).

Johanna feels happier and less alone since she has discovered a true friend—and sort of a lover—in Ken, who has already begun to open up to her. Therefore, the central theme of this tale is loneliness as a path to happiness. Johanna takes a gamble and transforms her loneliness into happiness by leaving her old life behind to pursue something new when she is first alone and has no one to turn to for support. As previously demonstrated, Johanna is a powerful, solitary woman who makes friends with Sabitha after a false letter mishap. To put it simply, the author offers Johanna as an example of how independence may still lead to loneliness—in this case, because she lacks friends. Happiness will ultimately follow one who discovers her match and opens out to her world.

One friend's evil deed brought good to another through a letter. Like Johanna, Sabitha and Edith composed a letter to Sabitha's father, which they then posted to him. They found it amusing to trick his father under Johanna's name. As Johanna meets Ken through a letter address and takes care of him well during his illness, true love blossoms. Omar is their son, and

they had a happy marriage and good career. They surprisingly made a good life for Johanna with their funny letter. The English saying "Man Proposes, God Disposes" is quite well-known. People are free to develop any plans they like, but God only decides whether those plans will bear fruit or fail.

As we accomplish to the end of the component, we see that Alice Munro did a fantastic job of describing the lives of six characters, many of whom cross paths in unexpected ways. We learn more about the narrative and the people with every fresh viewpoint, and we are frequently taken away by the twist and turns of life.

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